

In the Memory of Hind Rajab

Poem

Aishi Saha

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1680-3314>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12628290

Introduction by the Author

The ongoing genocide in Gaza by the apartheid state of Israel has been continuing for more than six months now. It has taken countless innocent Palestinian lives including a large number of children and women. This poem is based on the state sanctioned murder of a six year old girl called Hind Rajab who was shot to death by the Israeli armed forces while she was trapped inside a car. It dramatises on the incident and retells it from the perspective of someone close to Hind.

In the Memory of Hind Rajab

- Aishi Saha

Hind, my dearest, no more does the bougainvillea bend
All canopy is dead. Your puppies trembled and shivered and then ran away,
Until they realized that every precarious alley was leading them back to this wasteland.
Mama's cereal rocket ships cannot feed those in the south,
But can surely kill them. When the sunlight falls ever so brightly,
The world says that God still loves Gaza. My faith is unshakeable.
It is not God I doubt, but the eulogizing poets of the imperialist world
Who want to make another Auschwitz-Birkenau out of our homeland.
My people do not want grandiose memorials of their tragedy,
Or a month dedicated to their history inaugurated by the murderous state(s) that erased it.
It is happening already – my daughter the topic of intellectual discourse
Learned white men condemning the murder over a coffee at Starbucks
They will stick Hind's name in bold characters on museum walls
'Never again,' they will say while they do it again to someone else.
For every stone we threw, they dropped bombs on starving children;
For every slogan we raised, they planted bullets in our lungs.
Hind, my dearest, I hope death carries you to the realm of our collective dream,
Where land beside the Jordan River meets the Mediterranean Sea,
Where you can hear the song of birds and not the blast of airstrikes,
Where children hold each other's hands and not each other's cold bodies,
Where every individual lives with grace without the fear of forced displacement.
There – Hind, wait for me. Wait for Palestine.

Glossary

Hind - Hind Rajab, a six year old girl shot to death by the Israeli armed forces.

Gaza - Gaza City is a Palestinian city in the Gaza Strip

Faith - Strong belief in somebody or something (Here refers Upon the Merciful ALLAH)

Auschwitz, Birkenau - A series of concentration camps operated by the Nazi state of Germany during World War II in occupied Poland.

Homeland - Native land (Here refers to Gaza)

Tragedy - A very sad event or situation, especially one that involves death.

Murderous State(s) - The countries that do genocide. For example- Sri Lankan genocide of the Tamils, Rwandan genocide of the Tutsis, Biafran Genocide of the Igbos, Jewish Genocide of the German Nazis (At present Israeli acts of war crimes in Gaza)

Starving children - Hungry children

Forced displacement - Coerced movement of someone away from their home land

Wait for Palestine - For the Liberty of Palestine

Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: Nil

Author (s) Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.